

THE EFFECTS OF MASTER SINTERING CURVE ON THE MICROSTRUCTURAL EVOLUTION AND MAGNETIC PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

This work reports our recent work on the fabrication of NiCuZn ferrites, with the particular interests on how the master sintering curve affect the microstructural evolution and magnetic properties of this materials. $\text{Ni}_x\text{Cu}_y\text{Zn}_z\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ ferrites were prepared using solid state reaction method. These ferrites were then pre-sintered under the sintering temperature of 700°C-900°C with the interval of 50°C. The shrinkage response and densification evolution of each pre-sintered materials was studied by dilatometric runs at constant heating rates of 10°C/min up to 1100°C. The master sintering curve (MSC) of each graded materials was constructed based on the combined-stage sintering model and validated by and non-isothermal sintering experiments. Microstructural and structural analyses were carried out using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and X-ray diffraction (XRD), respectively. The permeability of samples under the DC-bias superposition condition was measured by an Agilent LCR meter at the frequency of 1 MHz. In this work, the influences of pre-sintering on the apparent activation energy (Q), densification evolution and grain growth of NiCuZn ferrites were investigated. The experimental results demonstrated that the Q -value decreased to a lowest point of 577.6 kJ/mol with the increasing pre-sintering temperature up to 850°C. In addition, the magnetic properties including the behaviors of DC-bias superposition were also discussed by studying the MSC of ferrites in this article.

1 INTRODUCTION

Chip inductors are taking important roles in the latest electronic products such as cellular phones, video cameras, tablets, and computers, etc.. Meanwhile, small dimensions, lightweight and stronger function become the necessary requirements for chip inductors. Recently, surface mount technology (SMT) has been rapidly developed for the miniaturization and multi-functionalization of electronic devices, including multilayer chip inductors (MLCI). In the fabrication of MLCI, the NiCuZn ferrites is stacked alternately with the conducting inner electrode, usually silver paste, and then co-fired to obtain monolithic structure[1].

NiCuZn ferrites exhibit excellent magnetic properties in the high frequency, and can be sintered below the melting point of Ag (around 961°C). Previous investigations on this materials mainly centre on the issues: (a) Improving electromagnetic properties such as the electrical resistivity, permeability, DC-bias superposition and Q -factor etc., based on the microstructural optimizations[2-4]; (b) Promoting the co-firing effectiveness of NiCuZn ferrites with Ag electrode or other ceramics through using advanced sintering technique or doping a amount of additives[5,6].

Up to now, many routes to obtain ultra-fine NiCuZn ferrites have been explored, such as sol-gel method, co-precipitation, hydrothermal synthesis, spray drying and freeze-drying etc.[3,7,8]. But the preparation method of NiCuZn ferrites based on the solid state reaction route was still widely used, due to its advantages of low costs, high reproducibility, high volume production and conveniences on adjusting atomic ratio and studying additives. In this method, NiO, CuO, ZnO, Fe_2O_3 are usually taken as raw materials, then generally through steps of wet-milling, pre-sintering, and second milling to

fabricate NiCuZn ferrite powders[1]. Among them, properties of ferrites are highly sensitive to the pre-sintering conditions. It has been reported that an increased pre-sintering temperature could increase the sintered density and initial permeability[9]. However, how the pre-sintering conditions affect the densification behaviours, activation energy and DC-bias superposition behaviours have never been reported yet as to our best knowledge. This work reports our recent work on the fabrication of NiCuZn ferrites, with the particular interests on how the pre-sintering temperature and master sintering curve affect the microstructural evolution and magnetic properties of this materials.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The NiCuZn ferrite powders were synthesized by the solid state reaction route. Analytical grade NiO, CuO, ZnO, Fe₂O₃ raw materials were weighted according to the mole ratio of Ni:Cu:Zn:Fe=25:5:22:48, and wet-milled at 300 rpm for 4 hours using a high-energy planetary milling machine. The mixtures were dried and divided into five groups and pre-sintered at temperatures of 700°C, 750°C, 800°C, 850°C and 900°C for 4 hours in air to achieve single phase powders. Five groups of materials were denoted as P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 according to the pre-sintering temperature, respectively. After pre-sintering, the second milling process for five groups powders were conducted at the same condition. Then, each graded materials were pressed at a uniaxial pressure of 200 MPa to create bars of 4mm×3mm×3mm. Then the linear shrinkage of green bulks were monitored in a dilatometer with the heating rate (HR) of 10°C/min up to 1100°C in air. At least five samples of each group were measured to ensure experimental consistency. The accuracy of the measurements was found to be within ±0.1µm. The construction of master sintering curve was validated by three different non-isothermal sintering schedules under the consistent sintering condition using a laboratory furnace. Five groups of green compacts were heated up to a desired temperature at constant heating rate of 2, 5 and 10°C/min without a holding time and cooling down naturally.

Average particles size of ferrite powders pre-sintered at different temperatures was characterized using the laser diffraction particle size analyzer (BI200SM). The green density of pressed samples was measured using the Archimedean method. The phase structure of all samples was determined by X-ray diffractometer (XRD, D/max 2550PC, Cu-K α radiation). In order to investigate the initial permeability and DC-bias superposition behaviours, each graded powders were also pressed into toroidal shaped samples with outside diameter of 36mm, inside diameter of 22mm and height of 7mm. The toroidal pallets were also sintered at 1100°C with the heating rate of 10°C/min in air. The change on the permeability of consolidated samples under different DC-bias magnetic field was tested at the frequency of 1 MHz using the precision LCR meter (Tonghui 1776) and the DC-bias current source (Tonghui 2828S).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The exterior appearances of ferrite powders pre-sintered at 700°C, 750°C, 800°C, 850°C and 900°C, respectively. Samples with lower pre-sintering temperature exhibited the colour of fire brick. While the colour of powders turned into dark red with the increasing of pre-sintering temperature. The incomplete solid state reaction or residual oxides in the P700 and P750 powders may responsible for the discrepancy of exterior colour.

In Fig.1, the XRD analysis result for P850 and P900 sample shows a single phase of the cubic spinel structure for NiCuZn ferrites. Although the spinel phase can also be found in the samples with lower pre-sintering temperature, the existence of secondary phase revealed the incomplete solid state reaction. Peaks of CuO phase were appeared in the P750, P700 and P800 samples. Meanwhile, the peaks of spinal phase slightly moved towards the low-angle side, when the pre-sintering temperature increased. This can be explained by the fact that the radius of Cu²⁺ (0.087 nm) is larger than that of Fe³⁺ (0.065 nm) in the octahedral sites[10]. In addition, the broad diffraction lines exhibited were indicative of the fine particle nature of the ferrites. While, as the pre-sintering temperature increased, the peak sharpness and intensity increased due to the crystalline growth at higher temperature[11].

Figure 1: XRD patterns of P700 (a), P750 (b), P800 (c), P850 (d) and P900 (e) powders.

The particle size and green density of samples as a function of pre-sintering temperature are given in Fig.2. The pre-sintering temperature largely affected the particle size and green density of NiCuZn ferrites. The average particle size increased when the temperature was raised. The D50 for P900 was $1.91 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{m}$, which increased 8.5% compared to that of P850. At the higher temperature, some amounts of extra thermal energy enhanced the growth of particles size.

Figure 2: Average particle size and green density of P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 samples.

The green density of samples shows a similar trend with the particle size. The green density has a monotonous increase with the increasing pre-sintering temperature. The higher temperature led to a larger shrinkage of powders and reduced the closed pores among the particles, which could contribute to an increased molded density[12]. At the same cold pressing condition, the increased mobility of coarser sized particles also promoted a higher green density. H. Su et al. suggested that a high green density of compacts had a positive effect on improving sintered density[9]. However, when the pre-sintering temperature increased, the particles size enhanced along with the reduced lattice defects in the pre-sintered powders. The surface chemical activity of particles would impact the densification behaviours of materials during heating up. Thus, the investigations on the activation energy of sintering for these powders were conducted as to find how the pre-sintering influences the final density and properties.

The typical shrinkage vs. temperature profile of each graded materials was transformed into the evolution of density[13]. Fig.3 shows variations of density and densification rate during the heating up to 1100°C for P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 samples. Important parameters in this figure are given in Table 1. The final density revealed a different trend with the green density as the function of pre-sintering temperature. P850 sample possessed a higher final density than P900 and other samples.

At the same heating rate, the onset of shrinkage was found to marginally shift to lower temperature side as decreasing pre-sintering temperature. On the contrary, in the case of maximum shrinkage rate, samples synthesized at higher pre-sintering temperature could reach the highest densification rate at an earlier time. P900 sample reached the top densification rate at 809.4°C, which is 123.3°C lower than that of P700 sample.

Samples	Temperature at the Onset of Shrinkage (°C)	Temperature at the Maximum Shrinkage Rate (°C)	Relative Density at 1100°C (%)
P700	710.5	932.7	91.81
P750	714.0	925.8	92.05
P800	738.5	833.2	91.80
P850	758.2	815.3	95.39
P900	773.5	809.4	92.73

Table 1: Temperatures at different shrinkage rate and sintered density for each graded samples

Figure 3: Density and densification rate as a function of sintering temperature for P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 compacts.

The mass transport plays the major role in the sintering process. From the thermodynamic viewpoint, the intrinsic driving force for sintering is the reduction of the total interfacial energy. It depends only on the initial and final states of the thermodynamic parameters describing the overall process. To make sintering happens, a minimum energy must be input to the system in order to jump the potential energy barrier that prevents atoms from diffusing with the solid. This minimum energy is known by sintering activation energy[14]. In order to further study the sintering behaviours of NiCuZn ferrites, the concept of master sintering curve (MSC) was used to determine the sintering activation energy of each graded samples.

The formulation and construction of MSC is derived from combined-stage sintering, which extends the analysis of sintering beyond the confined segments described by individual stage models[15,16]. For a given powder and green body, the instantaneous relationship between sintering activation energy and relative physical density could be established through the construction of MSC, which can be demonstrated by the equation as given[16],

$$\Theta(t, T(t)) \equiv \int_0^t \frac{1}{T} \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) dt \quad (1)$$

Where $\Theta(t, T(t))$ is a function of the thermal history, t is the time, R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, Q is the activation energy of sintering. In the construction of MSC, an optimum value of activation energy is in Eq.(2) is determined and $\rho-\Theta(t, T(t))$ trajectory is constructed for

heating profiles. The $\rho-\Theta(t, T(t))$ data are fitted to a sigmoidal curve. If the value of Q is unknown, it can be estimated from the Θ vs. ρ data. If the correct value of Q has been estimated, all data points should fall on a single sigmoidal curve. When the data points cannot converge, a new Q is chosen and the above steps are iterated until the particulate value is decided.

According to the above description, the MSC for each graded samples was constructed based on the densification profile during the sintering with the heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ up to 1100°C . Before applying the constructed MSC into the present investigation, the validity of MSC should be verified through a sufficient amount of sintering experiments. As an example, Fig. 4 gives the constructed fitting curve for P700 sample with the activation energy of 747.2 kJ/mol . The mean residual square is 0.001492 . In addition, the MSC for P700 was validated by three types of non-isothermal sintering experiments. The results have given well agreements between the fitting curve and validation experiments. In addition, the density profile versus time-temperature integral could predict the final density sintered at a given temperature, irrespective of the heating path.

Figure 4: Validation of MSC for P700 compact. The non-isothermal experimental results of three sintering cycles agreed well with fitting curve at 747.2 kJ/mol .

Figure 5: Activation energy during the non-isothermal sintering of P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 compacts based on the construction of MSC.

The sintering activation energy for P750, P800, P850 and P900 compacts was also calculated and verified using the same method. Calculation results are given in Fig. 5. It is clearly to observe that the

activation energy decreased with the increasing of pre-sintering temperature up to 850°C, and then increased to a higher value. When the temperature was lower than 800°C, the residual CuO produced from the incomplete solid state reaction greatly increased the activation energy of green compacts during the sintering process, made the consolidation of pre-sintered powders becomes relatively difficult[17]. While as the temperature continued increasing to 900°C, the powders particle size increased, and more lattice defects in pre-sintered NiCuZn powders could be revised, thus increased the activation energy[9]. This is the main reason to the lower final density of P900 sample, compared to that of P850 sample.

Fig. 6 The variations of permeability as a function of direct current bias for P700, P750, P800, P850 and P900 compacts.

In Fig.6, the initial permeability (μ_i) increased with the pre-sintering temperature increased up to 850°C, then dramatically decreased with the pre-sintering temperature continued increasing to 850°C. μ_i of P850 sample was higher than that of others, which can be ascribed to its higher density. The permeability of ferrites can be practically determined by two different magnetizing mechanisms: $\mu=1+x_{spin}+x_{dw}$. Where x_{spin} and x_{dw} represent the magnetic susceptibility of spin and domain wall motion, respectively[18]. The spin contribution is closely related to the sintered density, which is increased by promoting density. In addition, closed pores in lower density samples disturb the movement of domain wall, so that the initial permeability decreases when closed pores exist[11]. Fig.6 also shows the typical relationship between permeability and DC-bias current, which indicates that the permeability will decrease with the increase of the DC-bias superposition magnetic field. The curves of all graded samples exhibited the same trend, which experiencing a plateau at the beginning, then decreasing swiftly and gradually declining at the end. Noticeably, the DC-bias superposition characteristics of samples do not reveal a linear relationship with the pre-sintering temperature. P900 sample exhibits a minimum value of decline ratios at the loaded DC-bias current of 3A and 5A, which are 25.18% and 38.95%, respectively. But the initial permeability for P900 is relatively low, and is insufficient for developing the power application of MLCI. Meanwhile, P850 sample revealed a higher initial permeability and a favorable ability to retard the decrease of permeability.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of pre-sintering temperature and master sintering curve on the density evolutions, phase transformation, microstructure and DC-bias superposition characteristic of NiCuZn ferrites were investigated experimentally. The residual CuO existed in the samples with lower pre-sintering temperature, which would increase the activation energy during the sintering process. Increased pre-sintering temperature could improve DC-bias superposition characteristic. Powders pre-sintered at temperature of 850°C exhibited the lowest value of activation energy, 577.6 kJ/mol, and promoted the compromise between the permeability and DC-bias superposition.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Imanaka, *Multilayered low temperature cofired ceramics (LTCC) technology*, Springer, USA, 2005.
- [2] H.I. Hsiang and J.L. Wu, Copper-rich phase segregation effects on the magnetic properties and DC-bias-superposition characteristic of NiCuZn ferrites, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, **374**, 2015, pp. 367-371.
- [3] K. Sun, Z. Lan, Z. Yu, X. Jiang and J. Huang, Phase formation, grain growth and magnetic properties of NiCuZn ferrite, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, **323**, 2011, pp. 927-932.
- [4] S. Yan, L. Dong, Z. Chen, X. Wang and Z.K. Feng, The effect of the microstructures on the DC-bias superposition characteristic of NiCuZn ferrite, *Journal of Magnetism and Magnetic Materials*, **353**, 2014, pp. 47-50.
- [5] L. Huan, X. Tang, H. Su, H. Zhang, Y. Jing and B. Liu, Effects of SnO₂ on DC-bias-superposition characteristic of the low-temperature-fired NiCuZn ferrites, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, **50**, 2014, pp. 2006104.
- [6] Q. Yang, H. Zhang, Y. Liu, Q. Wen and L. Jia, Microstructure and magnetic properties of microwave sintered NiCuZn ferrite for application in LTCC devices, *Materials Letter*, **79**, 2012, pp. 103-105.
- [7] Z. Yue, L. Li, H. Zhang and Z. Gui, Preparation and characterization of NiCuZn ferrite nanocrystalline powders by auto-combustion of nitrate-gels, *Materials Science and Engineering B*, **64**, 1999, pp. 68-72.
- [8] M.A. Gabal, Y.M.A. Angari, A.Y. Obaid and A. Qusti, Structural analysis and magnetic properties of nanocrystalline NiCuZn ferrites synthesized via a novel gelatin method, *Advanced Powder Technology*, **25**, 2014, pp. 457-461.
- [9] H. Su, H. Zhang, X. Tang, Z. Zhong and F. Bai, Influences of high calcinations temperature on densification and magnetic properties of low-temperature-fired NiCuZn ferrites, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, **47**, 2011, pp. 4328-4331.
- [10] T.T. Ahmed, I.Z. Rahman and M.A. Rahman, Study on the properties of the copper substituted NiZn ferrites, *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, **153-154**, 2004, pp. 797-803.
- [11] H.I. Hsiang, C.S. His, R.L. Lin and C.Y. Chiang, Addition of a minor amount of Co₂Y effects on the microstructure, magnetic properties and DC-bias superposition characteristic of low-fire NiCuZn ferrites, *Materials Chemistry and Physics*, **151**, 2015, pp. 295-300.
- [12] J.S. Kim and C.W. Ham, The effect of calcining temperature on the magnetic properties of the ultra-fine NiCuZn ferrites, *Materials Research Bulletin*, **44**, 2009, pp. 633-637.
- [13] C.X. Ouyang, S.G. Zhu, J. Ma and H.X. Qu, Master sintering curve of nanocomposite WC-MgO powder compacts, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, **518**, 2012, pp. 27-31.
- [14] S.J.L. Kang, *Sintering: Densification, grain growth, and microstructure*, Oxford, UK, 2005.
- [15] J. Hansen, R.P. Rusin, M. Teng and D.L. Johnson, Combined-stage sintering model, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, **75**, 1992, pp. 1129-1135.
- [16] H. Su and D.L. Johnson, Master sintering curve: a practical approach to sintering, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, **79**, 1996, pp. 3211-3217.
- [17] R.A. Mondal, B.S. Murty and V.R.K. Murthy, Temperature and frequency dependent electrical properties of NiCuZn ferrite with CuO-rich grain boundary segregation, *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, **595**, 2014, pp. 206-212.
- [18] M.T. Johnson and E.G. Visser, A coherent model for the complex permeability in polycrystalline ferrites, *IEEE Transactions on Magnetics*, **26**, 1990, pp. 1987-1989.